

Effect of Temperature on the Intrinsic Viscosity and Unperturbed Dimension of Polymethylmethacrylate and Polystyrene in a Mixture of Two Non-Solvents (Co-solvents)

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The effect of temperature on the Intrinsic Viscosity of Polystyrene (PS) in cyclohexane-acetone media and Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) in Carbon tetrachloride-*n*-alcohol mixtures has been studied. For the PS-cyclohexane-acetone system, the temperature coefficient of $[\eta]$ is positive at the optimum solvent composition but negative on either side of it. In the case of the PMMA-Carbon tetrachloride-*n*-alcohol systems however $[\eta]$ is rather insensitive to a change of temperature showing a very small positive temperature coefficient for all compositions including the optimum. So the idea that $\frac{d[\eta]}{dT}$ is directly related to solvent power appears to be untenable in such systems.

IN connection with our work on cosolvency of polymers in a mixture of two non-solvents, we measured the change in intrinsic viscosity over the whole accessible range of composition to test whether the optimum solvent composition has the lowest $\frac{d[\eta]}{dT}$ as expected from theory¹. The expectation did not come true and we report here the main results. According to Fox-Flory treatment of linear-flexible chains based on Flory's excluded volume treatment of dilute polymer solutions¹, the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ is determined not only by the expansion factor α but also by K which involves $(\bar{r}_0^2)^{3/2}$, \bar{r}_0^2 being the mean square end-to-end chain distance at θ temperature.

$$\text{i.e. } [\eta] = KM^{1/2}\alpha^3 \quad \dots (a)$$

$$\text{and } K = \phi(\bar{r}_0^2/M)^{3/2} \quad \dots (b)$$

The expansion factor α naturally increases with temperature but \bar{r}_0^2 though supposed to be a constant for a given polymer-solvent system actually decreases slightly with increase of temperature due to change in interaction parameter and entropy parameter and other factors. Anyway, both these variations are rather small and act in opposite sense as a result of which the variation of $[\eta]$ is very small of the order of 0.1% per degree. In very good solvents $[\eta]$ should decrease with increase of temperature, in an athermal solvent $[\eta]$ should be effectively independent of temperature but in a poor solvent $[\eta]$ should increase with increase of temperature. The increase should be most rapid at temperatures near the theta temperature and experimental results for flexible chain polymers are in general agreement with these predictions.

Experimental

Materials :

Polymer Preparation and Fractionation : Styrene and methylmethacrylate (MMA) were purified according to standard methods and polymerised thermally. The polymers were fractionated by usual methods in benzene using methanol as precipitant.

Solvents used were all of A.R. grade. The alcohols have been refluxed with a small amount of sodium before distillation.

Measurement of Intrinsic Viscosity :

Solution viscosities of the different polymers were determined by measuring the flow time in an Ubbelohde dilution viscometer for which kinetic energy corrections are negligible. $[\eta]$ was calculated using the inverse form of Schulz-Blaschke equation² viz.

$$\frac{c}{\eta_{sp}} = \frac{1}{[\eta]} - k'c \quad (1)$$

Molecular Weights :

Viscosity average molecular weights of PMMA and PS were determined at 30° in benzene from the $[\eta]$ - M relationships², (1) for PS and (2) for PMMA.

Results and Discussion

1. Effect of Temperature on Intrinsic Viscosity :

(a) PS in cyclohexane-acetone media :

It is evident from Fig. 1 that at optimum solvent composition the temperature coefficient of intrinsic

Fig. 1. Variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature for polystyrene in cyclohexane-acetone media.

viscosity is positive and on the two sides of it negative. Hence the interesting conclusion arises that on both sides of the optimum, there should be a composition where the temperature coefficient of $[\eta]$ is zero. Since a positive $\frac{d[\eta]}{dT}$ is generally interpreted¹ as poor solvent power, a contradiction is noted at the optimum solvent composition. It is clear that such interpretation is not valid in this case of cosolvent mixtures. k' changes in a manner opposite to that of $[\eta]$. Results are stated in Table 1.

(b) PMMA in Carbon tetrachloride-*n*-alcohol media :

PMMA in carbon tetrachloride-*n*-alcohol media behaves in quite a different way, $d[\eta]/dT$ being always positive (Figs. 2 and 3). However, the temperature coefficient is negligible for the PMMA- CCl_4 -ethanol system although a definite optimum solvent composition is present. The CCl_4 -propanol system behaves in a peculiar fashion as is evident from Fig. 3. It is expected that a definite optimum must be present (which we have failed to detect) and the system is moderately sensitive to temperature. It is evident from Table 1 that there is a lack of a sharp optimum in the case of CCl_4 -butanol system and it is insensitive to temperature. So it appears that the usual theory of variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature is not applicable to polymer cosolvent system. This is probably due to the fact that the relative solvation may change with temperature and create complications. On the whole, the effect of temperature changes on $[\eta]$ is not very marked. It follows from this directly that the effect on k' is also not marked.

II. Effect of Temperature on the Unperturbed Dimensions :

We have tried to utilise the intrinsic viscosity data to determine the unperturbed dimensions with the help of an equation of Deb and Palit⁴, viz.,

$$\langle \bar{r}_0^2 \rangle | M \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left[\frac{[\eta]_{k'=0.44T}}{2.87 \times 10^{21} M^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right]^{\frac{2}{3}} \dots (2)$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON $[\eta]$ and k' (BRACKETTED VALUES ARE k' VALUES)

Temperature °C	22	24	26	28	30	32	34	36	38
PS in cyclohexane-acetone									
$[\eta]$ dl/g in									
28 : 72				0.60(0.67)	0.56(0.71)	0.56(0.58)	0.57(0.40)	0.54(0.75)	0.54(0.79)
67 : 33				0.77(0.45)	0.86(0.42)	0.90(0.36)	0.93(0.20)	0.95(0.17)	
(optimum)									
90 : 10							0.66(0.28)	0.65(0.29)	0.64(0.38)
PMMA in CCl_4 -methanol									
$[\eta]$ dl/g in									
60 : 40	0.79(0.07)	0.80(0.07)	0.81(0.07)	0.82(0.06)	0.83(0.04)				
85 : 15									
(optimum)	0.87(0.14)	0.89(0.13)	0.91(0.09)	0.92(0.09)	0.94(0.09)				
95 : 5		0.74(0.30)	0.74(0.27)	0.77(0.26)	0.78(0.25)	0.80(0.22)			
PMMA in CCl_4 -ethanol									
$[\eta]$ dl/g in									
60 : 40				0.72(0.13)	0.73(0.13)	0.74(0.13)	0.77(0.12)		
88 : 17			3.02(0.95)	3.13(0.91)	3.14(0.87)	3.17(0.85)			
(optimum)									
90 : 10	2.44(0.15)	2.56(0.13)	2.67(0.12)		2.74(0.09)	2.82(0.09)	2.99(0.06)		
PMMA in CCl_4 -propanol									
$[\eta]$ dl/g in									
60 : 40				4.44(0.14)	4.61(0.13)	4.85(0.13)	5.05(0.08)		
79 : 21				1.38(0.67)	1.49(0.39)	1.52(0.33)	1.56(0.27)		
90 : 10				1.45(0.09)	1.46(0.09)	1.46(0.08)	1.47(0.07)		
PMMA in CCl_4 -butanol									
$[\eta]$ dl/g in									
60 : 40				1.07(0.14)	1.13(0.13)	1.16(0.08)	1.19(0.07)		
75 : 25				1.13(0.25)	1.15(0.24)	1.19(0.23)	1.25(0.16)		
(optimum)									
90 : 10				1.11(0.17)	1.18(0.16)	1.20(0.12)	1.24(0.07)		

where $[\eta]_{k'=0.447}$ is obtained by interpolation from a plot of $\frac{1}{[\eta]}$ versus k' at $k'=0.447$.

Unfortunately, however, the plot here is not linear in practically all cases and so any extrapolation to obtain the value of $[\eta]_{k'=0.447}$ is somewhat uncertain. In spite of this uncertainty we obtained satisfactory values for PS in cyclohexane-acetone, e.g. 673×10^{-11} and 691×10^{-11} compared to 710×10^{-11} obtained by Schultz⁵ and 735×10^{-11} by Flory⁶. In the case of PMMA, the values vary within a wide range, depending on the temperature and the alcohol. It is still somewhat gratifying to note that the unperturbed dimension $(\langle r_0^2 \rangle / M)^{\frac{1}{2}}$

Fig. 2. Variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature for polymethylmethacrylate in CCl_4 -methanol.

Fig. 3. Variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature for polymethylmethacrylate in CCl_4 -propanol.

varies from 674×10^{-11} to 724×10^{-11} for CCl_4 -methanol, 742×10^{-11} to 997×10^{-11} for CCl_4 -propanol and for CCl_4 -butanol from 786×10^{-11} to 806×10^{-11} which compare not too badly with the literature value of 680×10^{-11} , considering the uncertainty introduced in such extrapolation.

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